

The credit risk management practices of microfinance institutions in Batangas province: Basis for improvement

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Abstract

This study focused on the Credit Risk Management Practices of Microfinance Institutions in Batangas Province and their implications for the financial inclusivity of the MFIs. Specifically, this paper determined the profile of the subject MFIs, the level of Financial Inclusion, the Extent of Practice of MFIs in each phase of CRM, the significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables, the considerable difference between FI and CRM when grouped according to profile variables, and to propose a strategy based on the findings where improvements can still be made. The study utilized the descriptive-quantitative research design. A researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather data from 51 out of 72 sample MFIs in Batangas Province that were chosen using Convenient-Non-Probability Sampling. The study used frequency and percentages, weighted mean and composite mean, Spearman Rho method, compare means, and a 4-point scale, as statistical treatment. It is revealed that most MFIs in Batangas Province have already established their operations. Further, the findings showed that the majority of the MFIs in Batangas Province approved only less than 5,000 clients with less than 1 million loans outstanding as of 2021, which indicates that they approved small loans to a small number of clients and thus small loans outstanding for the year. The study concluded that MFIs in Batangas Province are financially inclusive, as evidenced by the high level of each financial inclusion component; quality has the highest composite mean, while usage has the lowest composite mean. The findings showed that MFIs are practicing MFI CRM "to a great extent", as evidenced by high composite means in each phase of the CRM Process - having Communication and Consultation and the Scope, Context, and Criteria as the highest composite mean, and assessment as the lowest composite mean. This research also revealed a significant relationship between Financial Inclusion and CRM Practices, but no significant difference between Financial Inclusion and CRM when grouped according to profile variables was also depicted. Finally, proposed strategies for improving CRM Practices of MFIs have been constructed.

Keywords: Microfinance institutions; credit risk management practices; financial inclusion; Batangas Province.

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Introduction

The sudden strike of the pandemic causes a massive escalation of risks in different industries in the economy, which leads to business losses, additional expenses, and, in the worst cases, business failure and bankruptcy. Among those risks, credit risk is the oldest problem for businesses, especially those in the banking and financial industries. It is the risk that a creditor might encounter when a borrower fails or delays paying back the whole or part of the loan, resulting in a loss. This paper discusses credit risk management from the point of view of a microfinance institution.

Using the level of non-performing loans as a parameter to see the level of credit risk present in the global, local, and microfinance industries, several articles and statistics performed by the World Bank, Census and Economic Information Centre (CEIC), Asian Development Bank, and Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) claim the increasing level of non-performing loans present in the country's banking system. The Philippines has continuously increased in rank among countries with high levels of non-performing loans since 2017. As part of the banking sector, microfinance institutions, the subject of this study, despite increasing borrowers and outstanding loans, have the lowest loan quality as they have the highest nonperforming loans (NPLs) with 31.20%. According to Ferreira (2023), the development of non-performing loans is influenced by market conditions, particularly the concentration and competition of the bank market as well as regulatory frameworks, in addition to bank performance as evaluated by efficiency and profitability, but ensuring increased economic growth is the best approach to diminishing the number of non-performing loans.

The International Finance Corporation substantiated this allegation, stating that the most significant source of risk for microfinance institutions was their loan portfolios, necessitating the need for credit risk management (CRM). Further, Shresta (2021) states that loan default was a challenge for MFIs because borrowing significantly increased while risk management remained inadequate. But as these quasi-banking institutions became exposed to a greater degree of credit risk by often lending with no collateral to underprivileged individuals who do not have access to formal banking services, they played a vital role in achieving a financially inclusive society. The BSP recognizes the role of MFIs in the development of the country and its economy. In the middle of justifying how MFI assists financial inclusion while exposing themselves to a greater degree of credit risk, the Calabarzon Region and the Batangas Province can be found at the center of the discussion of both variables. According to the BSP RED 2020 Report, Calabarzon has had the highest number of microfinance loans and the highest number of microfinance borrowers for two consecutive years. Meanwhile, Batangas, the research locale, is in the Top 10 with the highest Financial Inclusion Index, based on the Report on the State of Financial Inclusion in the Philippines (BSP, 2017; Luis, 2018).

Ngonyani (2019) studied the impact of credit risk management practices on the performance of microfinance institutions in Tanzania, where it was revealed that the credit supervision practices have impacted the portfolio at risk of the MFIs. Laar and Adjei (2020) conducted a study showing that CRM has a negative relationship with performance in the banking sector; thus, the rise in credit risk management increases performance. Tharouma (2022) stated in their study that financial inclusion in Algeria remains relatively low compared to global levels. Another study by Lekhelebana (2022) said that the current policy and procedures are insufficient for the loan book, which has worsened its performance over time.

Despite these arguments, it is determined that studies about MFIs' credit risk management remain inadequate since the field of empirical research mostly focuses on banks. This gives rise to the research gap that this study tries to fill. This study adopts a concrete foundation as it is anchored in two relevant and reliable frameworks. The first framework is the ISO 31000:2018 Risk Management Framework, established by the International Organization for Standardization. This framework has been used in this study as the independent variable, adapted in the context of credit risk, to derive the Credit Risk Management Process (Karim, 2019). This process has six phases, namely: (a) communication and consultation; (b) scope, context, and criteria; (c) assessment; (d) treatment; (e) monitoring and review; and (f) recording and reporting.

On the other hand, the BSP National Strategy for Financial Inclusion's Financial Inclusion Components were used as the dependent variable (Llanto & Rosellon, 2017). This framework has four components, namely: (a) access; (b) usage; (c) quality; and (d) welfare. These two reliable frameworks were the premise of this study to be able to attain its rationale of analyzing the credit risk management practices of MFIs in Batangas Province and proposing a strategy for improving them. To be specific, this study aims: (1) To determine what is the profile of the subject microfinance institutions; (2) To determine the level of financial inclusion of MFIs; (3) To determine the extent of the practice of the credit risk management process; (4) To determine if there is a significant relationship between financial inclusion components and credit risk management practices, which also entails our null hypothesis 1; (5) To determine if there is a significant difference between financial inclusion components and credit risk management practices when grouped according to profile, which also tries to prove our null hypothesis 2; and (6) To propose strategies for improving MFIs' credit risk management practices.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive research design, quantitative in approach, to describe the MFIs' credit risk management practices, assess their financial inclusion level, and determine the presence of significant relationships and differences when the profile variable intervenes. The researchers believed that a descriptive research design was an excellent choice since the goal of the study was to analyze and describe the variables.

The researchers used convenient nonprobability sampling to distribute questionnaires to respondents. A convenience sample is a non-probability sample in which the researcher selects subjects who live nearby and are available to participate in the research study.

After using the Raosoft Calculator, the researchers derived 72 as the sample from the determined population of 87 MFIs in the province. The study's respondents are the managers of the MFIs that operate in Batangas Province because they are engaged in product development, capacity building, and the implementation of risk management policies. Out of the 72 MFI managers targeted, only 51 participated in this study, which is equivalent to 70.83% of the sample size or 62.20% of the total population of MFIs in Batangas Province. The reason for not attaining the targeted sample size was that managers needed to be more responsive or refuse to participate due to their strict confidentiality policy. In these 51 participating MFI managers, 45 answered via Google Forms, while the remaining six answered through pen and paper.

The researchers used a set of questionnaires as the main instrument for gathering information, which was prepared based on the statement of the problem. A reliability test was conducted, and it resulted in a 0.988 using Cronbach's Alpha, which indicates that the instrument is reliable and can help attain the objective of the study. The survey questionnaire was divided into four parts. The first part covered the microfinance institution profile, which includes the number of years in operation, the number of approved customers in 2021, and several loans outstanding as of 2021. The second part consisted of questions about financial inclusion components, including access, quality, usage, and welfare. The third part was the credit risk management practices used by MFIs, including communication and consultation, scope, context, and criteria, assessment, credit risk treatment, monitoring and review, and recording of the credit risk management process. Each of the phases contained five (5) questions. The items listed were based on the study's framework, ISO 31000:2018. The fourth and final section was allotted for recommendations and suggestions from the respondents. For instance, the researchers made a Google Form-type questionnaire for the respondents, which was sent through their social media accounts for those who could not reach them face-to-face. On the other hand, the researchers also used a hard copy of the questionnaires for those respondents who could be reached face-to-face by the researchers.

The set of questionnaires prepared by the researchers was checked and validated by the research adviser and research experts. The validated questionnaire further underwent reliability testing, and a statistician processed the results. The instrument passed reliability tests and is ready for distribution. A printed copy of the questionnaire was provided by the researchers, and attached to the letter to the respondents are the Data Privacy Provisions to increase their confidence in participating. And then, the researchers conducted a confidential survey by sending email survey links to target MFI email addresses and Facebook pages and reaching out to friends and colleagues who have connections to MFIs. After gathering the data, the results were tallied, tabulated, and interpreted using statistical treatments and mathematical approaches.

Results and Discussion

Profile of MFIs

Table 1. Number of Years in Operation of MFIs

Number of Years in Operation	Frequency	Percentage
1 year and below	5	9.80
More than 1 year but less than 5 years	20	39.22
More than 5 years but less than 10 years	7	13.73
More than 10 years	19	37.25
Total	51	100.00

The majority of the MFIs were within the range of more than one year but less than five years in their number of years of operations. It comprised 39.22% of MFI participants, or 20 out of 51. Next on the highest were the MFIs who were more than ten years in operations with 37.25%, 13.73% of the MFIs had operations of more than five years but less than five years and the least of them were the MFIs having one year and below with 9.80%.

Table 2. Number of Approved Clients in 2021 of MFIs

Number of Approved Clients in 2021	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1,000 Clients	20	39.22
1,000 to 5,000 Clients	20	39.22
5,000 to 10,000 Clients	4	7.84
More than 10,000 Clients	7	13.73
Total	51	100.00

Most of the MFIs had less than 1,000 approved clients in 2021, 39.22% or 20 out of 51. Tied up at the top were the MFIs that had 1,000 to 5,000 approved clients. MFIs with more than 10,000 approved clients in 2021 and 5,000 to 10,000 approved clients in 2021 were 7 (13.73%) and 4 (7.84%), respectively.

Table 3. Number of Loans Outstanding in 2021 of MFIs

Number of Loans Outstanding in 2021	Frequency	Percentage
100 million pesos and below	38	74.51
More than 100 million pesos but less than 500 million pesos	6	11.76
More than 500 million pesos but less than 1 billion pesos	2	3.92
More than 1 billion pesos	5	9.80
Total	51	100.00

The majority of the MFIs participated comprising 74.51% or 38 out of 51 belonged to those with 100 million pesos and below outstanding loans as of 2021. MFIs with more than 100 million pesos but less than 500 million pesos loans outstanding as of 2021 were 6 or 11.76%. 5 or 9.80% has more than 1 billion pesos loans outstanding. The remaining 2 out of 51 MFI participants belonged to those with more than 500 million pesos but less than 1 billion pesos loans outstanding as of 2021.

Financial Inclusions of MFIs

1. **Access.** Access emphasizes the formal institution's production and availability of financial products and services. Table 4 shows the financial inclusion of MFIs in terms of access.

Table 4. Financial Inclusion of MFIs in Terms of Access

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Provides financial products and services to the public.	3.43	H	1.33
2. Makes the financial product and services available and accessible.	3.43	H	1.33
3. Ensures that their location and methods are of wide range to reach the public.	3.43	H	1.33
4. Considers the barriers present in financial products and services available.	3.33	H	5
5. Intends to reach the underprivileged community through their products and services.	3.39	H	4
Composite Mean	3.40	H	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 – 1.49 – Low (L)

Highest among the items that the MFIs did to be financially inclusive in terms of access were providing financial products and services to the public; making financial products and services available and accessible; and ensuring the location and methods are of wide range to reach the public, all having the weighted mean of 3.43. Last in the position, with a weighted mean of 3.33, was the consideration of MFIs of the barriers present in their financial products and services.

2. **Quality.** Quality is the consumers' experience, as seen by their attitudes and opinions concerning the things that are now available to them. The financial inclusion of MFIs in terms of quality is shown in table 5.

Table 5. Financial Inclusion of MFIs in Terms of Quality

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Considers the lifestyle and needs of the users of their financial products and services.	3.43	H	2.5
2. Matches the needs of customers through their products and services attributes.	3.43	H	2.5
3. Satisfies their customers with the financial products and services they offered.	3.41	H	4
4. Considers the needs of their customers in their product development.	3.45	H	1
5. Ensures that their clients have access to all relevant information on financial products and services to make informed decisions.	3.37	H	5
Composite Mean	3.42	H	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 – 1.49 – Low (L)

With a 3.45 weighted mean, the MFIs considering the needs of their customers in their product development ranked as top 1. Last in the rank, with a weighted mean of 3.37, was the MFIs ensuring that their clients had access to all relevant information on financial products and services to make informed decisions.

3. **Usage.** Usage is the extent to which different financial goods and services are used and the patterns of use. Table 6 presents the financial inclusion of MFIs in terms of usage.

Table 6. Financial Inclusion of MFIs in Terms of Usage

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Measures what combination of financial products are used by anyone person or household.	3.14	MH	5
2. Focuses more on the depth of financial service/product use.	3.25	H	4
3. Identifies the factors that influence individuals' decisions to use credit services.	3.33	H	2
4. Provides quality financial products and services that make customers frequently avail and for a long time.	3.51	H	1
5. Determines what a customer uses a combination of financial products and services.	3.29	H	3
Composite Mean	3.42	H	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 -1.49 – Low (L)

MFIs providing quality financial products and services that make customers frequently available and, for a long time, got the highest weighted mean of 3.51 and ranked first. With a weighted mean of 3.14 and a moderately high verbal interpretation, MFIs measuring the combination of financial products used by any person or household ranked fifth.

4. **Welfare.** It is achieved when a financial product or service affects consumers' lives, such as through changes in spending, business activity, and well-being. The financial inclusion of MFIs in terms of welfare is presented in table 7.

Table 7. Financial Inclusion of MFIs in Terms of Welfare

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Influences the livelihoods of the customers in terms of personal/business productivity.	3.41	H	2.5
2. Strengthens the social capital of the clients it serves (through careful group formation, collective action, cooperation towards common goals, relationships with other programs, facilitation of access to previously inaccessible services, etc.).	3.41	H	2.5
3. Increases its clients' influence with local or national government (the MFI individually or through the participation in MFIs' networks).	3.27	H	5
4. Encourages equitable and long-term business practice.	3.33	H	4
5. Supports economic development and sustainability.	3.49	H	1
Composite Mean	3.38	H	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 -1.49 – Low (L)

MFIs assisting economic development and sustainability ranked first with a weighted average of 3.49. The MFIs boosting their clients' influence with the local or national government had the lowest weighted mean of 3.27.

5. **Summary of Composite Mean of the Level of MFIs Financial Inclusion.** To provide consolidated values and interpretations, a summary of the composite mean of the level of MFIs financial inclusion is necessary (Ozili, 2023). This is to determine which components the MFIs do with the lowest composite mean. Table 8 shows the summary of a composite mean of the level of MFIs financial inclusion.

Table 8. Summary of the Composite Mean of the Level of MFI Financial Inclusion

Financial Inclusion Components	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Access	3.40	H	2
Quality	3.42	H	1
Usage	3.31	H	4
Welfare	3.38	H	3

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 -1.49 – Low (L)

Table 8 depicts that all MFIs are financially inclusive in terms of different components of financial inclusion. They are highest in the Quality component with a composite mean of 3.42, followed by Access with a 3.40 combined mean. Next is the Welfare component with a 3.38 composite mean, and with the lowest composite mean of 3.31, the Usage.

The following results may be related to Operaña (2016). In his study, they stated that financial inclusion initiatives began in the micro-finance industry, which created goods and services for low-income consumers or impoverished portions of the community. The study reported that 50% of Filipino adults are satisfied with their transactions with access points, including MFIs. Further, in terms of welfare, the perspective of Filipino adults about financial services was shown that 86 percent of Filipino individuals feel that financial goods and services are vital, 88 percent believe they are helpful, and 87 percent wish to have access to official financial institutions like MFIs. In terms of formal financial institution product and service usage, the BSP stated that 47 percent of Filipino adults borrowed money from formal financial institutions, 24.5 percent saved money, and 31.3 percent had accounts at formal financial institutions. However, adult Filipino usage of financial products and services is lower when compared to other nations (Aguirre-Cayanan, 2023; Maouloud et al., 2022).

Credit Risk Management Practices

1. **Credit Risk Communication and Consultation.** The goals of credit risk communication and consultation are to help key stakeholders understand risk, the rationale for decisions, and why specific actions are required. Table 9 shows the CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of communication and consultation.

Table 9. CRM Practices of the MFIs in terms of Communication and Consultation

Statements The MFL...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Sets good communication channels between the employees that enable them to perform their tasks soundly and correctly with regard to credit risk management.	3.49	GE	2
2. Ensures that all employees of the MFI are aware of and understand credit risk and credit risk management practices.	3.53	GE	1
3. Establishes relevant and reliable credit risk information systems to track operations, goal progress, and compliance.	3.45	GE	3
4. Ensures that different views are appropriately considered when defining credit risk criteria and evaluating credit risks.	3.41	GE	4
5. Organizes a meeting with all stakeholders to address and debate credit risk and management concerns.	3.37	GE	5
Composite Mean	3.45	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

MFIs ensuring that all employees of the MFI are aware of and understand credit risk and risk management practices ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.53. Last in the standings were MFIs organizing a meeting with all stakeholders and debating credit risk and management concerns, weighed in at 3.37.

2. Credit Risk Scope, Context, and Criteria. The goal of defining the scope, context, and criteria is to tailor the risk management process so that effective risk assessment and treatment can take place. Table 10 shows the results of the CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of scope, context, and criteria.

Table 10. CRM Practices of the MFIs in terms of Scope, Context, and Criteria

Statements The MFL...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Adapts the credit risk management takes in the context of the objectives and activities of the organization.	3.29	GE	5
2. Is aware of the internal and external environment of the company.	3.33	GE	4
3. Is aware of the scope of the risk management implementation.	3.41	GE	1.5
4. Develops criteria in-line with the company objectives and policies.	3.37	GE	3
5. Establishes a clear and valid scope, context, and criteria for credit risk.	3.41	GE	1.5
Composite Mean	3.36	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

Both earned the first rank with a weighted mean of 3.41 were the MFIs aware of the company's internal and external environments and the MFIs established a clear and valid scope, context, and credit risk criteria. Ranking last were the MFIs modifying the credit risk management that considers the organization's objectives and activities with a weighted mean of 3.29.

3. Credit Risk Assessment. Credit Risk Assessment is the comprehensive process of credit risk identification, credit risk analysis, and credit risk evaluation. Table 11 shows the CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of assessment.

Table 11. CRM Practices of the MFIs in terms of Assessment

Statements The MFL...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Identifies any material changes that might affect the credit risk management process and structure and develop corrective actions.	3.22	ME	5
2. Defines its credit risk policies.	3.41	GE	1
3. Assess the CRM regularly, and their changes are handled properly.	3.27	GE	3.5
4. Takes into account the causes and credit risk sources, including its consequences and likelihood to occur.	3.27	GE	3.5
5. Conducts deliberations and evaluations to credit its risks and decides what appropriate action to be implemented.	3.35	GE	2
Composite Mean	3.31	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

First in the rank was the weighted mean of 3.41, which indicated that MFIs were great at defining their credit risk policies. Gathered the lowest weighted mean of 3.22, MFIs identifying any material changes that might affect the credit risk management process and structure and developing corrective actions got a moderate degree of verbal interpretation.

4. Credit Risk Treatment. Credit risk treatment aims to choose and implement risk-reduction strategies. Table 12 shows the CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of treatment.

Table 12. Financial Inclusion of MFIs in Terms of Treatment

Statements The MFL...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Formulates and selects credit risk treatment options.	3.29	GE	5
2. Consults the professionals on the best treatment to treat credit risk.	3.37	GE	2.5
3. Treats the credit risks in a timely and relevant manner.	3.37	GE	2.5
4. Manages the credit risks through the application of controls.	3.41	GE	1
5. Uses risk-sharing treatment by sharing their risks from one party to another.	3.31	GE	4
Composite Mean	3.35	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

The highest ranking with an average rating of 3.41 was the MFI controlling credit risks through implementing controls. MFIs formulating and selecting credit risk treatment options ranked last, with a mean score of 3.29.

5. Credit Risk Monitoring and Review. The goal of monitoring and review is to ensure that process design, execution, and outcomes are of high quality and effectiveness. Table 13 depicts the CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of monitoring and review.

Table 13. CRM Practices of the MFIs in terms of Monitoring and Review

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Performs a periodical review of implemented credit risk management.	3.27	GE	4.5
2. Tracks all corrective actions and ensures they are implemented and working as intended.	3.37	GE	1
3. Sets an ongoing or separate evaluation that enables the MFI's management to determine whether internal control over financial reporting is functioning.	3.35	GE	2
4. Checks that the internal and external environment has not changed to affect the credit risk.	3.27	GE	4.5
5. Evaluates whether the credit risk management framework, plan, and policy are still relevant.	3.31	GE	3
Composite Mean	3.32	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

MFI, in tracking all corrective actions and ensuring they were implemented and working as intended, obtains a 3.37 weighted mean and was ranked first. Last was MFI, in performing a periodical review of implemented credit risk management and checking that the internal and external environment had not changed to affect the credit risk, both gained a 3.27 weighted mean.

6. Credit Risk Recording and Reporting. The risk management process and outcomes should be documented and reported through suitable channels in credit risk recording and reporting. The CRM practices of the MFIs in terms of recording and reporting is presented in Table 14.

Table 14. CRM Practices of the MFIs in terms of Recording and Reporting

Statements The MFI...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Records the credit risk strategy, policies, and outcomes throughout the organization.	3.39	GE	3.5
2. Compiles the records of the processes of credit risk management on time.	3.41	GE	2
3. Keeps the credit risk management activities and results for future decision-making.	3.49	GE	1
4. Ensures that the data assist the interaction with stakeholders of the MFI.	3.35	GE	5
5. Considers the differences in stakeholders and their specific information needs and requirements for reporting.	3.39	GE	3.5
Composite Mean	3.41	GE	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – Great Extent (GE); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderate Extent (ME); 1.50 – 2.49 – Less Extent (LE); 1.00 -1.49 – Least Extent (LEE)

The MFIs kept credit risk management activities and results for future decision-making ranked first, with a weighted mean of 3.49. At last, with a weighted mean of 3.35, MFIs ensuring that the data assists the MFI's interaction with stakeholders.

7. Summary of Composite Mean of the Extent of MFIs Practice of Credit Risk Management Processes. To provide consolidated values and interpretations, a summary of a composite mean of the extent of the practice of MFIs in each phase of the CRM Process is necessary. This is to determine which phase the MFIs are with the lowest and highest composite mean. Table 15 shows the summary.

Table 8. Summary of the Composite Mean of the Extent of Practice of MFIs in each Phase of Credit Risk Management Processes

Phases of Credit Risk Management Processes	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Communication and Consultation	3.45	GE	1.5
Scope, Context and Criteria	3.45	GE	1.5
Assessment	3.31	GE	6
Treatment	3.35	GE	4
Recording and Reporting	3.41	GE	3
Monitoring and Review	3.32	GE	5

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 – High (H); 2.50 – 3.49 - Moderately High (MH); 1.50 – 2.49 – Moderately Low (ML); 1.00 -1.49 – Low (L)

Table 15 depicts that all MFIs receive a “Great Extent” of practice in each phase of credit risk management processes. They have the highest composite mean in Communication and Consultation and Scope, Context, and Criteria, with a composite mean of 3.45. Third in rank is Recording and Reporting, with a composite mean of 3.41. Ranked fourth is the practice of Treatment. Fifth is the practice of Monitoring and Review. Lastly, with the lowest mean of 3.31, is the extent of the practice in Assessment.

Credit risk assessment has the lowest composite mean. Kiawa (2015) stated that risk identification in credit risk management ensures that the risk management function is established throughout the entire operation. It helps sort risks according to their importance and assists management in developing risk management strategies to allocate resources efficiently. This, in turn, assists the management of micro-finance institutions in implementing risk-mitigation measures, which improves the efficiency of the institutions' services.

In summary, MFIs are performing well in terms of credit risk management. Their practices show the great extent to which they take measures to deal with credit risk. The study by Korir (2014) shows the same result about the extent of MFI CRM practices. The findings show that five out of six participating MFIs are adapting CRM practices. Further, out of those MFIs, 4 are performing CRM practices, particularly in credit risk control, to a great extent, 1 to a Very Great Extent, and the other 1 to a moderate extent.

Similarly, the study of Ssekiziyivu et al. (2017) also reveals the same. 90.01% of their respondents confirm that they are adopting CRM practices. 61.5% of the MFIs agreed to a great extent about their risk management.

The cited findings are consistent with the current study where CRM practices are performed "great extent," and with regards to the adoption of CRM in the Philippines, it is a must, as BSP regulated this. However, though they are practicing well in CRM today, the uncertainty of the future may induce inapplicability or inadequacy of their current CRM. As such, a continuous improvement must be made. In the evaluation performed by the International Finance Corporation, MFIs frequently demonstrate tremendous CRM potential for improvement, which can lead to major difficulties whenever credit risk develops, and the MFI's capacity to cope with it is challenged.

Relationship between the Financial Inclusion Components and Credit Risk Management Practices

Financial inclusion components and credit risk management practices are the variables of this study. Financial inclusion is dependent, and credit risk management practice is the independent variable. Having sound credit risk management practices allows MFIs to operate effectively and sustainably, reaching more clients and achieving financial inclusion.

1. **Access and Credit Risk Management Practices.** Table 16 shows the relationship between access and credit risk management processes.

Table 16. Relationship between Access and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	.456	0.001	Significant	Reject
SC_ALL	.581	0.000	Significant	Reject
ASS_ALL	.511	0.000	Significant	Reject
TR_ALL	.603	0.000	Significant	Reject
MON_ALL	.496	0.000	Significant	Reject
REC_ALL	.658	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

Communication and consultation and access had a computed value of 0.456 with a significance value of 0.001. The same goes for scope and criteria, with a 0.581 computed value, credit risk assessment had a computed value of 0.511, credit risk treatment had a calculated value of 0.603, credit risk monitoring and review proposed a computed value of 0.486, and credit risk recording and reporting had a value of 0.658. These phases had a significance level of 0.000. The significant relationship thus rejected the null hypothesis 1.

2. **Usage and Credit Risk Management Practices.** Table 17 shows the relationship between usage and the credit risk management process. Associating with usage, credit risk communication and consultation had a computed value of 0.589, credit risk context and criteria had a measured value of 0.619, and credit risk assessment had a projected number of 0.687. Furthermore, credit risk treatment had 0.680, credit risk monitoring and review had a value of 0.634, and recording and reporting credit risk had a corresponding value of 0.700. These phases had a significance level of 0.000. The significant relationship thus rejected the null hypothesis 1.

Table 17. Relationship between Usage and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	.589	0.000	Significant	Reject
SC_ALL	.619	0.000	Significant	Reject
ASS_ALL	.687	0.000	Significant	Reject
TR_ALL	.680	0.000	Significant	Reject
MON_ALL	.634	0.000	Significant	Reject
REC_ALL	.700	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

3. **Quality and Credit Risk Management Practices.** Table 18 shows the relationship between quality and the credit risk management practices.

Table 18. Relationship between Quality and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	.535	0.000	Significant	Reject
SC_ALL	.507	0.000	Significant	Reject
ASS_ALL	.573	0.000	Significant	Reject
TR_ALL	.568	0.000	Significant	Reject
MON_ALL	.548	0.000	Significant	Reject
REC_ALL	.563	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

The computed value for credit risk communication and consultation and quality was 0.535, credit risk scope, context, and criteria had a computed value of 0.507, credit risk assessment had a calculated value of 0.573, credit risk treatment had an estimated value of 0.568, credit risk monitoring and evaluation had a value of 0.548, and the recording and reporting of the credit risk management process had a computed value of 0.563. Each phase of the credit risk management process had a 0.000 significance level. The significant relationship thus rejected the null hypothesis 1.

4. **Welfare and Credit Risk Management Practices.** Table 18 shows the relationship between welfare and the credit risk management practices. The relationship between welfare, communication, and consultation presented a computed value of 0.520 and a significance value of 0.000. Aside from that, credit risk scope and criteria had a computed value of 0.549. Moreover, welfare and credit risk assessment signified a 0.574 computed value, and credit risk treatment got a value of 0.638. Credit risk monitoring and review obtained a computed value of 0.556. Likewise, a calculated value of 0.672 showed the connection between welfare and credit risk recording and reporting. The significant relationship thus rejected the null hypothesis 1.

Table 19. Relationship between Welfare and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	.520	0.000	Significant	Reject
SC_ALL	.549	0.000	Significant	Reject
ASS_ALL	.574	0.000	Significant	Reject
TR_ALL	.638	0.000	Significant	Reject
MON_ALL	.556	0.000	Significant	Reject
REC_ALL	.672	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 – Insignificant

5. Summary of the Relationship between Financial Inclusion and Credit Risk Management Practices. To assess whether there is a significant relationship and to reject the null hypothesis, a table summarizing the relationship between the financial inclusion components and the credit risk management practices is employed. Table 20 shows the summary.

Table 20. Summary of the Relationship between Financial Inclusion and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Access and CRM Process	Significant	Reject
Usage and CRM Process	Significant	Reject
Quality and CRM Process	Significant	Reject
Welfare and CRM Process	Significant	Reject

The data gathering and interpretation results show a significant relationship between financial inclusion components and credit risk management practices performed by MFIs. The values and interpretations in tables 16 to 19 signify this significant relationship. Kipchirchir's (2018) study may support this result, as her findings show that profit is firmly (p 0.05) connected favorably with credit policy while negatively correlated with default and risk coverage. Meanwhile, outreach had a substantial (p 0.05) inverse association with loan default and risk coverage but no link with credit policy. Thus, credit risk posed a barrier to MFIs' long-term expansion in terms of profit and reach (inclusion). As a result, proactive methods such as improved management information systems, better internal control, and rethinking customer-oriented goods should be explored.

With these findings, a significant relationship between credit risk and credit risk management and MFI outreach or the extent of reaching the public can reflect its financial inclusiveness. Hence, if credit risk has a negative impact on outreach (financial inclusion), its counter-activity in credit risk management practices is positively correlated to the financial inclusion of MFIS. A more financially inclusive operation will arise if credit risk management is excellent. It is because CRM gives rise to a high-quality loan portfolio. Credit allocation and risk management were essential to loan portfolio performance. The regression study revealed that credit allocation and risk management predicted 23.9 percent of loan portfolio performance (Ssekiziyivu et al., 2017).

A high-quality loan portfolio emphasizes a good CRM Process while providing financial products and services to the public and financial inclusion. Given the following results and supporting studies, the findings reject null hypothesis 1, as there is a significant relationship between financial inclusion and CRM practices.

Differences in Financial Inclusion Components and Credit Risk Management Practices when Grouped According to Profile

The profile variables determine if there is a significant difference in financial inclusion components and credit risk management practices of MFIs when grouped according to profile. Assessing this would answer the SOP 5 and accepts or reject the null hypothesis 2.

1. Number of Years in Operations. The difference on MFI Financial Inclusion Components when grouped according to the number of years in operation is shown in table 21.

Table 21. Difference on the MFI Level of FI Components in Terms of their Number of Years in Operation

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
ACC_ALL	1.874	0.147	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
Q_ALL	2.099	0.113	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
US_ALL	1.550	0.214	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
WEL_ALL	1.121	0.350	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: ACC – Access; Q – Quality; US – Usage; WEL – Welfare; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 – Insignificant

Access had a computed value of 1.874 and a significance of 0.147, quality had 2.099 and 0.113, usage had 1.550 and 0.214, and welfare had 1.121 and 0.350. The significant values, respectively, all imply insignificant differences and thus failed to reject null hypothesis number 2.

2. Number of Approved Clients in 2021. Table 22 shows the difference in MFI's Financial Inclusion Components when grouped according to the number of approved clients in 2021.

Table 22. Difference on the MFI Level of FI Components in Terms of their Number of Approved Clients in 2021

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
ACC_ALL	0.574	0.635	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
Q_ALL	0.304	0.822	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
US_ALL	0.207	0.891	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
WEL_ALL	0.251	0.860	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: ACC – Access; Q – Quality; US – Usage; WEL – Welfare; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 – Insignificant

Access had a computed value of 0.574 and a significance of 0.635, quality had 0.304 and 0.822, usage had 0.207 and 0.891, and welfare had 0.251 and 0.860. The significant values infer an insignificant difference and hence failed to reject the null hypothesis 2.

3. Number of Loans Outstanding as of 2021. The difference on MFI Financial Inclusion Components when grouped according to number of loans outstanding as of 2021 is shown in table 23.

Table 23. Difference on the MFI Level of FI Components in Terms of their Number of Loans Outstanding in 2021

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
ACC_ALL	0.019	0.996	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
Q_ALL	0.375	0.771	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
US_ALL	0.358	0.783	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
WEL_ALL	0.051	0.984	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: ACC – Access; Q – Quality; US – Usage; WEL – Welfare; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

Access had a computed value of 0.019 with a significance of 0.996, quality had a calculated value of 0.375 with a significance of 0.771, usage components had a computed value of 0.358 with a significance of 0.783, and welfare had a computed value of 0.051 with a significance of 0.984. As a result, it failed to reject null hypothesis 2.

4. Number of Years in Operation. The difference in MFI CRM Practices when grouped according to the number of years in operation is shown in table 24.

Table 24. Differences in the MFI Extent of CRM Practices in Terms of their Number of Years in Operations

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	0.276	0.842	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
SC_ALL	0.632	0.598	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
ASS_ALL	1.554	0.213	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
TR_ALL	0.780	0.511	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
MON_ALL	1.370	0.263	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
REC_ALL	0.670	0.575	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

The computed value of communication and consultation is 0.276, with a significance value of 0.842. Scope, context, and criteria showed a computed value of 0.632 and a significance value of 0.598. Risk assessment had a computed value of 1.554 and a significance value of 0.213. Treatment had a computed value of 0.780 and a significance value of 0.511. Credit risk monitoring and review proposed a computed value of 1.370 and a significance value of 0.263. Finally, credit risk recording and reporting had a calculated value of 0.670 and a significance value of 0.575. The insignificance thus failed to reject null hypothesis 2.

5. Number of Approved Clients in 2021. The difference in MFI CRM when grouped according to the number of approved clients in 2021 is shown in table 25. The scope, context, and criteria had a computed value of 0.166 and a significance value of 0.919; the assessment component had a computed value of 0.218 and a significance of 0.883; the treatment component had a measured value of 0.286 and a significance level of 0.835; the monitoring component had a computed value of 0.288 and a significance of 0.834; and lastly, the recording and reporting had a computed value of 0.166 and a significance of 0.876. As a result, it failed to reject null hypothesis 2.

Table 25. Differences in the MFI Extent of CRM Practices in Terms of their Number of Approved Clients in 2021

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	0.166	0.919	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
SC_ALL	0.189	0.904	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
ASS_ALL	0.218	0.883	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
TR_ALL	0.286	0.835	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
MON_ALL	0.288	0.834	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
REC_ALL	0.228	0.876	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

6. Number of Loans Outstanding as of 2021. The difference in MFI CRM when grouped according to the number of loans outstanding as of 2021 is shown in table 26.

Table 26. Relationship between Quality and Credit Risk Management Practices

Variables	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
COMM_ALL	0.591	0.624	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
SC_ALL	0.724	0.543	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
ASS_ALL	0.278	0.841	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
TR_ALL	0.341	0.796	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
MON_ALL	0.375	0.772	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
REC_ALL	0.509	0.678	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Legend: COMM – Communication and Consultation; SC – Scope, Context, and Criteria; ASS – Assessment; TR – Treatment; MON – Monitoring and Review; REC – Recording and Reporting; p-value < 0.05 – Significant; p-value > 0.05 - Insignificant

Communication and consultation had a computed value of 0.591 and a significance value of 0.624, scope, context, and, criteria had 0.724 and 0.543, assessment has 0.278 and 0.841, treatment had 0.341 and 0.796, monitoring had 0.375 and 0.772, and recording and reporting had 0.509 and 0.678 values respectively. The insignificance thus failed to reject null hypothesis 2.

7. Summary of Difference in Financial Inclusion Components and Credit Risk Management Practices of MFIs when Grouped According to Profile.

The summary of the differences in MFI Financial Inclusion components and CRM when grouped according to profile is shown in table 27. Table 27 shows that MFIs' level of financial inclusion and extension of practice in each phase of the credit risk management process, when grouped according to profile variables, shows no significant differences. Tables 21 to 23 show a significance value of higher than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between MFIs' levels of financial inclusion in each component when grouped according to profile variables. Moreover, tables 24 to 26 similarly infer results that have a significance value of higher than 0.05, which further indicates that there is no significant difference between the extent of MFIs' CRM practices when grouped according to profile variables.

Table 27. Summary of Differences in the MFI Level of Financial Inclusion and Extent of Credit Risk Management Practices When Grouped According to Profile

Variables	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
FI Components in terms of Number of Years in Operation	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
FI Components in terms of Number of Approved Clients in 2021	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
FI Components in terms of Number of Loans Outstanding as of 2021	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
CRM Practices in terms of Number of Years in Operation	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
CRM Practices in terms of Number of Approved Clients in 2021	Insignificant	Failed To Reject
CRM Practices in terms of Number of Loans Outstanding as of 2021	Insignificant	Failed To Reject

Table 27 shows that MFIs' level of financial inclusion and extension of practice in each phase of the credit risk management process, when grouped according to profile variables, shows no significant differences. Tables 21 to 23 show a significance value of higher than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between MFIs' levels of financial inclusion in each component when grouped according to profile variables. Moreover, tables 24 to 26 similarly infer results that have a significance value of higher than 0.05, which further indicates that there is no significant difference between the extent of MFIs' CRM practices when grouped according to profile variables.

The summary table shows a not significant verbal interpretation between the differences and hence fails to reject the null hypothesis 2. The insignificant difference in the level of financial inclusion when grouped according to the profile can be associated with the increasing demand for small financial products which MFIs offer due to the effects of the pandemic and the growing support of governmental laws for small lenders like MFIs for financial inclusiveness.

According to Taneja (2021), at the commencement of the COVID-19 pandemic, microfinance was put to the test. Microfinance institutions, which run a high-touch business and serve a lower-income clientele, which the epidemic has adversely damaged, were predicted to become extinct. Microfinance institutions, on the other hand, not only survived the recession but are today recognized as more robust and vital than ever. Furthermore, authorities have been particularly supportive of microfinance, balancing the interests of microfinance institutions (liquidity and loan portfolio quality) with the needs of micro-borrowers (loan obligations). With this, it may be inferred that regardless of the number of years in operation, number of approving clients, and number of loans outstanding, MFIs are financially inclusive, and their levels of FI are not far from one another.

Table 27 also shows a not significant verbal interpretation of the extent of CRM Practices when grouped according to profile variables. The findings of the study of Caya et al. (2018) support this as their study indicates that there is no significant difference in lending institutions when grouped according to profile, such as the number of borrowers, capitalization, and year in operation.

Proposed Credit Risk Management Strategies

Rationale

Effective credit risk management is required to remain compliant in today's strictly regulated environment and can provide a considerable business advantage if done correctly. Credit risk management must keep credit risk exposure within acceptable and appropriate boundaries. CRM is the most typically addressed risk by MFIs due to its inherent qualities and its immediate impact on their major earning asset, the loan portfolio. The profitability and stability of a microfinance institution are solely dependent on its credit risk management practices. The researchers would like to propose a material containing necessary information about which aspects of the credit risk management process are weak for MFIs and its recommended strategy for improvement.

Basic Premises of the Strategies

The proposed credit risk management strategies are based on the following premises:

1. The proposed strategies are formulated for each phase of the ISO 31000:2018 risk management process.
2. The proposed strategies for improving credit risk management enhance the credit risk management of microfinance institutions.
3. The enhancement of any strategies for improving credit risk management lies within the management of microfinance institutions.
4. The proposed strategies are formulated to be deemed applicable to microfinance institutions.
5. The proposed strategies are based on the study's findings relative to the current practices of microfinance institutions in credit risk management. It should be emphasized, however, that there is still opportunity to enhance in order to get greater outcomes.

Objectives

The primary objectives of credit risk management are to implement sound, appropriate credit processes that provide informed risk-taking, as well as guidelines for effective credit risk communication and consultation, scope, context, and criteria, assessment, treatment, monitoring, and review, and recording and reporting the credit risk management process. Credit risk management is one of the most important processes for MFIs, and the ability to manage it is critical to their success. Proper credit management will increase the MFI's profitability, thereby increasing shareholder wealth, and can make sure that the MFI generates enough positive credit from its operations to fund its deposit and lending activities indefinitely.

The following are the specific objectives of this plan:

1. To inform MFIs about which parts of their credit risk management process are inadequate.
2. To propose strategies to improve their credit risk management controls.

Concluding Statement

Putting effective credit risk management procedures in place will assist MFIs in correctly assessing and managing credit risk, thereby minimizing the severity of a loss. Moreover, in order to manage their portfolios and drive future growth, MFIs will balance their risks and opportunities in order to serve the public with confidence in the direction of financial inclusion.

Conclusions

The majority of the MFIs in Batangas Province already have an established market and impact on the society, as evidenced by their more than one year of operations. However, the number of approved clients in 2021 is in the two lowest ranges in the middle of the pandemic. Further, the number of loans outstanding is still low since MFIs have low loan portfolios and a limited amount of credit to be approved as prescribed by law, and still due to the effect of the pandemic.

MFIs in Batangas Province are financially inclusive and perform exemplary in each Financial Inclusion component. MFIs also show a great extent of practice in each Credit Risk Management Process phase. Overall, the MFIs are implementing sound practices about Credit Risk Management in each phase.

There is a significant relationship between the Financial Inclusion components and the credit risk management practices. This implies that the independent variable – Credit Risk Management Process, when implemented properly and effectively, will result in a positive impact in the dependent variable – the financial inclusion. There are no significant differences between the level of financial inclusion of MFIs in each component when grouped according to profile. There is a difference, but the difference significant value is not enough to reject the null hypothesis 2. This implies that the level of financial inclusion of MFIs in each component of financial inclusion is not significantly different from one another, based on their number of years in operations, number of approved clients as of 2021, and number of loans outstanding as of 2021. There is no significant difference between the extent of practices of the MFI credit risk management process when grouped according to the profile variable. This implies that the extent of the practice of MFIs in each phase of the CRM Process is not significantly different from one another, based on their number of years in operations, number of approved clients as of 2021, and number of loans outstanding as of 2021.

The proposed strategies will improve the CRM practices of the MFIs and further improve their operations towards financial inclusivity. Each of the items within the six (6) areas of consideration in the proposed strategy will assist the management of the MFIs, regulatory bodies for MFIs, and even other parties interested in improving their CRM.

Recommendations

The proposed strategies may be endorsed to Industry Experts and Research Enthusiasts, whose forte is in the field of finance and credit risk management, for further checking and validation of their applicability and effectivity. The proposed strategies may be implemented by the MFIs.

This study may be replicated to include new variables like other forms of risks present in microfinance institutions like operation, market, and strategic risks and be conducted outside Batangas Province. To the management of the MFIs, it is a must to continue to improve the credit risk management practices of MFIs to be able to adapt to the uncertainty imposed on the financial industry, the economy, and the society as a whole. It is also recommended to continue and improve the initiatives and endeavors of the microfinance industry to be able to provide more opportunities and assistance to people that are far from the reach of banking institutions.

To the regulatory bodies of MFIs, concrete assistance to MFIs should be established and improved, given the increasing role of these financial institutions in the society. To the future researchers whose studies are in-line with the credit risk management practices of MFIs, it is highly recommended to use Financial Performance as the dependent variable and to increase the number of population and samples by broadening the locale of the research or including other non-bank financial institutions as the subject of the research, and to use a simpler theoretical framework for guidance. To the researchers whose study is in-line with the financial inclusivity of MFIs, it is suggested to focus on quality and welfare since it is wider in context, and the studies relating to these two are very limited.

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